

Design of concrete mixtures and prediction of their compressive strength using machine learning

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Abstract. The use of machine learning and neural networks in predicting the compressive strength of concrete promises to significantly improve the accuracy and reliability of models for the design and optimization of concrete mixtures. With rapid advances in this field, computational models will be able to handle even larger amounts of experimental data, increasing their ability to capture the complex relationships between input parameters and the mechanical properties of concrete. With the development of new neural network architectures and machine learning algorithms, it will be possible to create highly adaptive predictive models that can better respond to variability in concrete composition and production conditions, leading to more efficient and sustainable design in the construction industry. The submitted paper deals with the design of concrete mixtures and prediction of their compressive strength based on the compressive strength results of mixtures of known composition from other experiments using machine learning. Practical validation of the developed regression model will be carried out by testing the machine-designed mixtures for compressive strength after 28 days.

1 Introduction

Concrete is one of the most widely used building materials in the world due to its availability, properties and wide range of applications [1, 2]. Despite its widespread use, the proper design of concrete mixture is a challenge because its properties depend not only on the nature of the input materials and the production technology, but also on the maturation time of the mixture. In the construction industry, accurate prediction of the key properties of concrete is important not only for the safety and reliability of structures [3], but also for reducing costs and carbon footprint [4, 5]. The methods used to predict strength characteristics, such as experimental tests, are time and cost consuming. Therefore, many researches are currently exploring the use of modern, advanced methods such as machine learning [6-8] or deep learning using neural networks [9, 10] to predict concrete properties. Machine learning, as one of the most

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fundamental tools in the world of artificial intelligence, represents an innovative and relatively simple approach to solving civil engineering problems. Its main advantage, based on the analysis and processing of large amounts of data, is the ability to identify relationships and patterns obscure to conventional methods. In the practice of concrete mixture design, this means eliminating experimental testing while reducing financial costs and time, which is achieved by predicting the desired properties based on the composition of the concrete and its eventual subsequent optimization. Although machine learning is easier to understand compared to more advanced artificial intelligence methods, its effectiveness is largely influenced by several negative factors: the quality of the dataset, the time and cost associated with creating the model and the limited ability to handle complex relationships. Nevertheless, it has several advantages over deep learning, such as lower computational requirements or the suitability of using even smaller datasets. The issue of predicting the properties of concrete is particularly topical given the increasing demands for sustainability in the construction industry [11, 12]. The use of artificial intelligence in construction is a modern approach that can meet the requirements of reducing CO₂ emissions, efficient use of resources and improving concrete properties. After understanding the relationships between the constituents of simpler concrete mixtures, it would be possible to predict the properties of even more complex mixtures for computational models [13-18]. The aim of this paper is to validate the accuracy of predicting the compressive strength of concrete mixtures proposed by the developed machine learning model based on compressive strength data from other researches [19].

2 Experimental program

The making of the computational model was carried out in the Python programmatic language, using as a training dataset [19] with more than 1000 values of the compressive strength of cylinders with dimensions $\varnothing 150 \times 300$ mm calculated for different types of concrete mixtures with variable composition consisting of the following input materials: ordinary portland cement type I (classification according to *ASTM C150*), blast furnace slag, fly ash, water, coarse aggregate (up to 10 mm), fine aggregate (fineness module of 3) and plasticiser based on naphthalene-formaldehyde condensate and fatty acid copolymer. Cylinder compressive strength was subsequently measured at a time horizon of 1 - 365 days of age of the samples. After programming the computational model, a user-friendly environment was created, an example of which is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Environment of the app for predicting the cylinder compressive strength of concrete.

The user interface of the app (shown in Fig. 1) consists of a toolbar where the weight range of independent variables (input materials of the concrete mixture) and the age of the samples can be set. On the right side is displayed the volume of the concrete mix calculated based on the amount of input materials entered by the user. The individual components per 1 m³ of fresh concrete mix and the predicted cylinder compressive strength for the specified sample age are then calculated, along with a graphical, predicted development of cylinder compressive strength over time.

2.1 Programming of the computational model

After training and testing several types of regression models, the *Light Gradient Boosting Machine* model with root mean square error $RMSE = 4.9378$ (MPa) and coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.9046$ was chosen as the most appropriate model. After fine tuning of the tested models with 10 iterations and 100 folds and final fine tuning of the best fitting regression models with 5 iterations and 5 folds, the *Gradient Boosting Regressor* model with $RMSE = 3.9406$ (MPa) and $R^2 = 0.9491$ was selected as the optimal model, indicating the high ability of the model to explain the variability in the data with a relatively small deviation of the predicted cylinder compressive strength from the actual cylinder compressive strength. The quality of the prediction of the regression model could also be explained by the graph of prediction errors in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Graph of prediction errors of Gradient Boosting Regressor.

The graph in Fig. 2 shows two lines: the line of best fit and the line of identity. The line of identity represents the line of perfect prediction, where the predicted cylinder compressive strength values are equal to the actual ones. The line of best fit represents the best possible linear approximation that tries to best describe the relationship between the predicted cylinder compressive strength values and the actual ones. Most of the points in the graph are close to the identity line and the line of best fit has a small deviation from it, indicating the high quality of the model.

2.2 Verification of the computational model on real samples

As mentioned in the previous chapter, the user environment contains a panel with input materials, whose interval represents the minimum and maximum values of a given input material obtained from the corresponding dataset [19]. After the user enters the weights of individual input materials, the given weights per 1 m³ of concrete mix are proportionally recalculated according to the respective volumetric weights of the materials. Since the one-day compressive strengths in the dataset contain only two values, the panel for the age of the sample is set from third day.

For the experimental testing of the computational model, two mixtures were randomly designed without any input requirements (the composition of which is given in **Table 1**). For each mixture, 7 cube samples with an edge length of 150 mm were prepared for logistical reasons, on which the cube compressive strength was performed after 28 days (due to standard *CSN EN 12390-3* [20]) and subsequently converted to the cylinder compressive strength (empirically determined as 80-85 % of the cube compressive strength). 28-day cube samples of both mixtures are illustrated in Fig. 3. In the practical part of the experiment, the used cement was portland cement CEM I 42.5 Hranice, in the case of blast furnace slag - granulated blast furnace slag JMS 420 Stramberk, then coarse aggregate 4-8 mm Litice, fine aggregate 0-4 mm Tovacov and a plasticizer based on polycarboxylate ethers.

Table 1. Designed concrete mixtures.

Input materials	Recalculated quantity kg·m ⁻³	
	ML1	ML4
Cement	377.44	571.59
Blast furnace slag	91.04	-
Fly ash	-	-
Water	166.73	187.35
Plasticizer	-	17.99
Coarse aggregate	933.88	903.96
Fine aggregate	901.15	747.30

Fig. 3. 28-day samples of mixtures ML1 (left) and ML4 (right).

Table 2 shows the cylinder compressive strength results for the interval 80-85 % of the cube compressive strength, the predicted compressive strength, the average deviation of the predicted values of the regression model from the actual values, and the average absolute deviation. In the case of the ML1 mixture, it can be observed that the actual absolute deviation (1.49 MPa) is lower than that of the regression model (3.94 MPa), so that in this case the computational model predicted the compressive strength of the cylinder quite accurately, while in the case of the ML4 mixture the absolute deviation (16.03 MPa) is approximately 4 times higher compared to that of the regression model (3.94), indicating its high inaccuracy in predicting the property.

Table 2. Observed properties and their statistical characteristics.

Mixture	Actual cylinder compressive strength [MPa]	Predicted cylinder compressive strength [MPa]	RMSE [MPa]	Average absolute deviation [MPa]
ML1	47.72 - 50.70	48.38	3.94	1.49
ML4	43.74 - 46.47	61.13		16.03

3 Conclusion

The proposed computational model represents a simplified form of predicting the compressive strength of concrete, dependent on its individual components. The model does not account for additional input parameters and factors influencing the final compressive strength, such as the water-cement ratio, chemical composition, specific surface area and reactivity of binder, mechanical properties of the aggregate, etc. Based on the provided data from the dataset [19], the importance of each variable in the computational model was determined, as its impact on the prediction of compressive strength (see graph in **Fig. 4**).

Fig. 4. The importance of individual variables in the prediction of compressive strength.

As can be seen from the graph in Figure 4, the variable cement has the most significant impact on the calculation (excluding the age of the samples), with a relative influence of more than 35%. In contrast, fly ash has a relative influence of approximately 1% on the prediction of compressive strength, which could indicate that it was used in only a small number of

cases (specifically 464 cases). However, the relative influence of coarse aggregate, which was used in all cases, is around 2%. Thus, these materials, within the specified range of usage quantities, have only a minimal effect on the prediction of compressive strength. To increase the predicted compressive strength, it is essential to prioritize the composition of cement and, to a considerable extent, also focus on water, plasticizers, and blast furnace slag.

The final regression model, *Gradient Boosting Regressor*, with a coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.9491$ and standard deviation $RMSE = 3.9406$ of the predicted versus actual compressive strength, appears to be suitable. This was confirmed on the ML1 mixture, where the model predicted the compressive strength after 28 days with an average absolute deviation of approximately 1.5 MPa. However, for the ML4 mixture, with an average absolute deviation of approximately 16 MPa between the actual and predicted values, this statement is false. It is also important to note that, in the practical part, the exact same input materials as those used in the dataset were not applied, which significantly affects the compressive strength results.

In future work, the model could be expanded by incorporating additional parameters such as water-cement ratio, material-specific properties, or curing conditions. Further development may also include testing more advanced machine learning algorithms and validating the model on larger and more diverse datasets to improve its generalization and practical applicability.

The data presented in this study are available on [21].

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